

Water fees for irrigated rice in Asia

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Because of increasing demand for domestic and industrial uses, water will be in short supply for agriculture, and it will be important to allocate and use water efficiently. Yet, because agricultural water prices are often low, farmers have little incentive to apply water efficiently to a given crop or to choose crops that economize on water use. The purpose of this paper is to document the level of water fees from various surface-water irrigation systems in different countries in Asia and to compare these fees to the costs of other important inputs used in production. Water fees (prices) are defined here as any financial charges levied by the government that allow farmers to divert water from irrigation canals constructed with government funds.

This paper uses data collected from six sites of the joint IRRI-national agricultural research systems project "Reversing Trends of Declining Productivity" (RTDP) located in India, Vietnam, China, the Philippines, Thailand, and Indonesia (Moya et al 2002). Irrigation at all of these sites is primarily from surface water and requires little or no government or communal pumping to reach farmers. All sites grow at least two rice crops per year and are located in the traditional "rice bowls" of Asia, where water is often plentiful (at least in the wet season) and, historically, little water is used by households and industry.

Surface-water fees are by far highest at sites in China and the Philippines (see table). Within China, agricultural surface-water

fees vary substantially across regions, depending on the relative degree of water scarcity. The data reported here come from Zhejiang Province, south of the Yangtze River, where water is much more plentiful than in the Yellow River Basin. Thus, although these water fees are the highest among the six sites, they are substantially lower than those on the north China plain. They are also lower than water fees reported by Moya et al (2001), which averaged US\$35 ha⁻¹ for two villages in the Zanghe Irrigation System in Hubei Province (located in the Yangtze River Basin). This varied within the system because fees depend on the quantity of water diverted by the farmers' irrigation group.

Throughout the Philippines, water fees are assessed in terms of a fixed quantity of rice (per hectare) valued at the government support price. This quantity is higher in the dry season than in the wet season. Because rice

prices are much higher in the Philippines than in neighboring countries, this partially explains the high absolute level of water fees. However, even as a share of gross revenue, water fees in the Philippines are still higher than in neighboring countries (with the exception of China). In the mid-1990s, water fees were about double current levels. However, the previous administration decided to lower fees in an effort to win the support of farmers.

While the level of water fees appears to be generally higher in China and the Philippines than at other sites in the survey, water fees are still substantially less of a burden for farmers than fertilizer costs. At these two sites, the share of water fees in gross revenue is closer to that of pesticides (see table).

Irrigation fees for farmers at RTDP sites in the other four countries were substantially lower than those in China and the Philippines. Farmers in Thailand and

Irrigation fees and fertilizer costs at six RTDP project sites, 1999.^a

Site	Irrigation cost (\$ ha ⁻¹ crop ⁻¹)	Fertilizer cost as share of gross revenues (%)	Irrigation cost as share of gross revenues (%)	Pesticide cost as share of gross revenues (%)
Aduthurai, Grand Anicut Dam, Cauvery Delta, Tamil Nadu, India	0	7	0.0	0.0
Cuu Long, Cantho, Mekong Delta, Vietnam	6	13	1.0	4.1
Jinhua, Zhejiang, China ^b	25	12	2.5	3.0
Nueva Ecija, Upper Pampanga River Irrigation System, Central Luzon, Philippines	13	7	1.5	2.2
Suphan Buri, Pho Phaya Irrigation System, Central Plain, Thailand	0	10	0.0	6.9
Sukamandi, Jatiluhur Irrigation System, West Java, Indonesia	4	5	0.5	4.3

^aData are averages of two crops. ^bData for China pertain to 1998.

India paid no water fees at all. While these areas may have a plentiful supply of water (at least in the wet season), the opportunity cost of using this water for other purposes will rise as economic development proceeds, and it will become increasingly important to allocate water more efficiently. The current system of low prices at these sites appears to hinder such efficient allocation.

References

- Moya P, Hong L, Dawe D, Chen CD. 2001. Comparative assessment of on-farm water-saving irrigation techniques in the Zhanghe Irrigation System. In: Proceedings of the International Workshop on Water-Saving Irrigation for Paddy Rice, March 2001, Wuhan, China.
- Moya P, Dawe D, Pabale D, Tiongco M, Chien NV, Devarajan S, Djatiharti A, Lai NX, Niyomvit L, Ping HX, Redondo G, Wardana P. 2001. The economics of intensively irrigated rice in Asia. In: Dobermann A, Witt C, Dawe D, editors. Increasing productivity of intensive rice systems through site-specific nutrient management. Los Baños (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute and Eufield, N.J. (USA): Science Publishers Inc. (in press)
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Farmers' participatory identification of gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason)-resistant rice varieties for desired characters

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Rice is cultivated on 24,000 ha, mostly under rainfed conditions, with an average production of approximately 1.1 t ha⁻¹ in Balaghat District of Madhya Pradesh, India. The average annual rainfall in the district is 1,600 mm, with 70% occurring from mid-June to late September. Consequently, nearly 70% of the rice area under medium and low-lying conditions is transplanted. Being located near gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason)-prone areas such as Raipur and Sakoli, the rice crop in the district suffers almost every year from attacks from this pest. The state government of Madhya Pradesh had introduced gall midge-resistant varieties such as Asha, Surekha, and IR36. However, farmers stopped growing resistant varieties, except for IR36, after one or two cropping seasons because they did not meet their requirements. Consequently, susceptible varieties (e.g., Kranti, Kulture, MW10) possessing characteristics desired by

farmers were adopted. In recent years, heavy gall midge attacks in the district compelled farmers to look for resistant varieties with the desired characteristics.

To reduce losses caused by the pest, factors that contributed to gall midge incidence were pinpointed for appropriate intervention and resistant rice varieties with the desired characters were identified through a three-phase farmers' participatory program in the district by IGAU from 1994 to 1997.

Through brainstorming sessions, interactive group discussions, and matrix ranking with 123 farmers from 36 villages and 21 rural agricultural extension officers, the factors contributing to gall midge incidence were identified in the first phase of the program (Table 1). In the second phase, 11 rice varieties (resistant as well as local susceptible varieties as checks) were collected from IGAU and local farmers. These were grown and evaluated by 125 farmers at four growth

Table 1. Factors that farmers think contributed to gall midge incidence in rice.

Factors (in order of priority)	
1	Lack of resistant varieties with desired characters and use of susceptible varieties
2	Unbalanced use of fertilizers—i.e., high N, less P, and little or no K
3	Continuous rain from July to September, resulting in waterlogging and making insecticides ineffective
4	No direct seeding and late transplanting because of dependence on rain
5	Summer rice cultivation and late harvesting just before the onset of the next cropping season, leading to pest multiplication
6	Late and suboptimal dose of insecticides
7	No preventive control measures and lack of alternative control measures
8	Poor technical know-how and poor economic conditions to combat pest attack
9	Dependence on unskilled laborers